

***DENOSUMAB DISCONTINUATION:
THE ABALOPARATIDE PLUS BISPHOSPHONATE
METRONOMIC SEQUENTIAL APPROACH***

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Abstract

Background. Discontinuing denosumab (Dmab) causes a rapid increase in bone resorption, loss of bone mineral density (BMD), and clusters of rebound-associated vertebral fractures (RAFV). Current approaches, such as intravenous (IV) zoledronate (Zol), oral bisphosphonates (BPs), teriparatide (TPTD), romosozumab (Romo), selective estrogen receptor modulators (SERMs), and menopausal hormone therapy (MHT), have failed to consistently provide protection.

Methods. We conducted a brief narrative review of randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational cohorts, and mechanistic studies, as well as expert position papers (2015-2025), that focused on post-Dmab strategies and mechanistic models of remodeling.

Results. Evidence consistently shows that Zol often requires repeated infusions and fails to prevent BMD decline or RAFV, especially after long-term Dmab therapy. Oral BPs are weaker and have limited adherence, TPTD worsens rebound resorption, and Romo provides only modest benefits. SERMs and MHT are largely ineffective. Once RAFV occurs, clinical outcomes remain poor despite rescue therapy. S. Bolamperti et al. suggested that complete osteoclast suppression abolishes coupling signals essential for bone formation, while BPs cannot neutralize osteomorph-driven resorption.

Hypothesis. We suggest that a metronomic BP regimen (low doses or extended intervals), combined (initially) with abaloparatide (Abalo) and guided by personalized monitoring of the C-terminal telopeptide of type I collagen (CTX), may limit osteoclast activity without stopping anabolic signaling, thus preventing fractures and maintaining bone-forming capacity.

Conclusions: A biologically informed, modulatory approach is a promising hypothesis that warrants future clinical testing and could redefine the paradigm of post-Dmab osteoporosis management.

Keywords: Denosumab, rebound, CTX, abaloparatide, alendronate, metronomic therapy, fractures, ECTS.

Introduction

Denosumab (Dmab) is a monoclonal antibody that effectively but reversibly reduces bone resorption, providing sustained decreases in fracture risk and incremental increases in bone mineral density (BMD). Dmab mimics osteoprotegerin (OPG, our endogenous decoy receptor) by binding to the receptor activator of nuclear factor κ B ligand (RANKL), thereby preventing its interaction with RANK, resulting in potent inhibition of osteoclast-mediated bone resorption [1,2]. However, its reversibility makes stopping treatment especially risky: bone turnover markers (BTMs), especially C-terminal telopeptide of type I collagen (CTX), rebound above pretreatment levels – often within months of the last injection – leading to BMD loss and clusters of vertebral fractures (VFs) [3-6].

Several strategies have been tested to reduce this rebound. Intravenous (IV) zoledronate (Zol) lowers the surge but often needs repeated doses and does not always reliably prevent fractures [7-9]. Oral bisphosphonates (BPs) are less effective and depend on adherence [7,10]. Teriparatide (TPTD) worsens rebound by increasing

resorption [11]. The effectiveness of romosozumab (Romo) appears to be suboptimal [12]. Selective estrogen receptor modulators (SERMs) and menopausal hormone therapy (MHT) are mostly ineffective [10,13].

When discontinuation is absolutely unavoidable, standard post-Dmab (consolidation) therapy typically involves IV Zol or an oral amino-BP, as recommended by the European Calcified Tissue Society (ECTS) position paper. The suggested therapeutic threshold of CTX levels less than 0.280 ng/mL indicates a need for antiresorptive treatment to prevent bone loss caused by rebound. In a recent study, a threshold of 0.212 ng/mL was proposed, based on 100% sensitivity in predicting bone loss in patients; however, this was derived from a small, ethnically diverse, and sex-specific cohort without fracture prediction, and the specificity remains unknown [7,9]. Therefore, real-world outcomes vary, but most patients require multiple doses of the (generally) most effective Zol, and some still experience BMD loss and/or fractures [8].

Recent clinical studies have reaffirmed these concerns. Kumar et al. demonstrated that rebound bone loss and VFs continue to be common in routine clinical practice, with BPs sequencing often showing inconsistency and being especially ineffective after long-term Dmab therapy [14]. Laursen et al. provided a comprehensive real-world overview, confirming both the clinical burden of Dmab discontinuation and the lack of a standardized, consistent exit strategy [15]. These findings underscore the urgent need for innovative approaches, such as novel ones based on mechanistic perspectives.

A ‘metronomic’ BP regimen—characterized by low-dose and/or less frequent BP administration to reduce total antiresorptive exposure compared to standard treatment—initially combined with the anabolic abaloparatide (Abalo), may decrease osteoclast overactivity by including an antiresorptive agent without disrupting osteoclast-osteoblast coupling signals (which are essential for anabolism), due to the lower exposure to the antiresorptive. In our approach, CTX values should be interpreted alongside the patient's individual characteristics, clinical, imaging, and CTX trend (considering baseline or local median CTX levels), with ‘0.280 ng/mL’ serving as a universal alert threshold and/or as a trend-based confirmation of discordant results.

Methods

We conducted a brief narrative review of the literature indexed in PubMed and Embase from 2015 to 2025, using terms like “denosumab discontinuation, rebound, CTX, bisphosphonate, teriparatide, abaloparatide, romosozumab, SERMs, hormone therapy, and fractures”.

We analyzed clinical studies, consensus statements, and mechanistic studies, focused on strategies and outcomes after Dmab withdrawal. Due to the variability of available data, results were summarized descriptively [16–19].

Then, we developed the metronomic BP-Abalo approach as a possible exit strategy post-Dmab, and to stimulate debate [20–22].

Results

Discontinuing Dmab consistently results in a characteristic and clinically dangerous situation. Within weeks of missing an injection, bone resorption markers, especially CTX, rise sharply, often exceeding pretreatment levels. Peak values typically occur between six and twelve months, sometimes more than doubling the baseline [3–6]. This biochemical increase is associated with a faster loss of BMD at the lumbar spine and hip [3,4], and it typically manifests with RAFV, often multiple and severely morphologic, occurring at rates significantly higher than those seen in untreated osteoporosis [5,6,12].

Among consolidation strategies, IV Zol is the most extensively studied. Randomized and observational data show that Zol, administered six months after the last Dmab dose, decreases but does not entirely prevent the rebound. Median CTX often rises to approximately 0.4 ng/mL, and VFs may occur in some patients [7,10]. Longer prior exposure to Dmab, especially beyond three years, is associated with poorer responses, characterized by incomplete CTX suppression and continued BMD loss despite Zol treatment [9,14]. Real-world series confirm that many patients undergo repeated infusions over several months, aiming to maintain partial control, which highlights the limited durability of this approach [8,11].

Oral amino-BPs, such as alendronate (ALN) and risedronate, have shown weaker efficacy compared to Zol. Their ability to prevent rebound seems limited, with higher rates of CTX overshoot and earlier BMD decline [7,24]. It is believed that adherence issues further reduce their effectiveness, and patients on long-term Dmab treatment rarely keep CTX below risk thresholds when switching to oral therapy [7].

Anabolic regimens have proven to be more problematic. Switching directly from Dmab to TPTD worsens the rebound dangerously: CTX levels spike higher than after Zol, BMD decreases at both the spine and hip, and VFs are not infrequent during treatment [11,15]. The option to combine TPTD with BPs provides partial protection against resorption. Still, it reduces the anabolic effect of TPTD, ultimately resulting in a weaker BMD increase compared to sequential regimens applied in other settings (where a BP follows TPTD) [16].

Romo has attracted interest due to its dual mechanism of action, as it acts both as a bone builder and as an antiresorptive agent. However, outcomes after Dmab were significantly reduced compared with those of Romo when not used in this sequence. Gains in BMD are modest, CTX suppression remains incomplete, and incident VFs have been reported despite therapy [12]. Even if a recent study showed that switching to Romo seemed to improve lumbar spine bone density (BMD) and quality (as indicated by an improvement in trabecular bone score, TBS) more effectively than continued Dmab, it did not entirely prevent rebound resorption [17].

SERMs and MHT have been studied in small series and showed limited or no effectiveness. Raloxifene was linked to a BMD decline back to pre-Dmab levels and an uncontrolled CTX rebound, while hormone therapy did not adequately suppress turnover [13].

Once RAFV occurs, treatment options become limited, and the prognosis is poor. Rescue with IV Zol or other amino-BPs is recommended (sometimes even requiring restarting Dmab), but new fractures often continue to cluster, despite prompt intervention [8,11]. Functional recovery remains incomplete, and patients remain at high risk of further events, highlighting the importance of effective preventive rather than reactive strategies [19,20].

At the mechanistic level, Dmab decoying of RANKL inhibits nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) and nuclear factor of activated T cells cytoplasmic 1 (NFATc1) signaling, reducing osteoclast differentiation and activity [1,2]. Osteoclast-derived coupling factors, such as transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), insulin-like growth factor-I (IGF-I), ephrinB2/EphB4, and sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P), are decreased, leading to “hibernating” basic multicellular units (BMUs) [21]. When treatment stops (about six months after the last injection), osteoclast precursors and osteomorphs (fusion-competent fragments) quickly reactivate as RANKL reappears, causing a resorptive surge reflected in CTX overshoot and rapid bone loss [23]. Emerging reports also show increases in circulating precursors during Dmab therapy, consistent with this biological mechanism [24].

Discussion

This narrative review confirms that discontinuation of Dmab is one of the most challenging aspects of osteoporosis management. Despite various strategies, none have consistently prevented the rebound phenomenon. IV Zol remains the most common and (generally) effective treatment. Still, even multiple infusions do not entirely prevent CTX increase, BMD loss, or VFs, especially in patients with long-term Dmab use [7–9,14]. Oral amino-BPs are generally weaker and limited by adherence issues, making them largely ineffective (especially) after extended treatment [7,24]. As seen, TPTD not only fails to offer protection but paradoxically worsens rebound resorption [11,15]. And despite Romo’s dual action, its effectiveness after Dmab is reduced, and fractures are reported [12,17]. Regarding SERMs and MHT, they appear to be substantially ineffective [13]. Then, when RAFV occurs, management becomes increasingly complicated and challenging, and no rescue therapy has been proven to be consistently efficacious [8,11,19,20].

These findings highlight the importance of developing and testing new approaches, trying to be more preventive than therapeutic, even experimenting with those that may extend beyond current in-label indications (when properly mechanistically and clinically justified). Last but not least, such a dangerous landscape reminds each prescriber of the need for extreme caution and planning before starting Dmab, considering our actual substantial inability to manage rebound in most cases adequately.

The limitations of current strategies become more evident when viewed in light of recent advances in bone biology. S. Bolamperti et al. reframe bone remodeling as an “operational process”, where osteoclast-mediated resorption provides essential signals for subsequent osteoblast-mediated formation, including TGF- β , IGF-I, Wnt5a, SLIT3, and RANK-carrying vesicles [21]. Under anti-RANKL therapy (Dmab), osteomorphs accumulate and quickly reactivate when RANKL is restored (after Dmab), fueling the rebound surge [21]. BPs, while reducing resorption, also distort osteoclast morphology and function, creating “BPs-osteoclasts” with impaired signaling capacity [21]. Moreover, they cannot directly neutralize osteomorphs, which explains why Zol fails to control rebound despite repeated dosing [9,14].

These mechanistic insights challenge the traditional view of total resorption blockade, where osteoclasts also deliver essential signals for osteoblast-driven formation. Instead, a carefully managed modulation of osteoclast activity is theoretically better – as enough to prevent a rebound increase but not so much that it disrupts the coupling signals necessary for bone formation [21].

Recent clinical reports partially support this interpretation. As said, Kumar et al. showed that BP consolidation is highly variable and becomes less effective after more than three years of Dmab therapy, with no standardized protocol for timing, drug choice, or duration [14]. Laursen et al. confirmed in a large-scale real-world study that there is both a clinical burden associated with discontinuation and unpredictability of outcomes despite consolidation [15]. Additionally, as mentioned earlier, Hong et al. demonstrated that Romo may improve lumbar spine BMD and TBS more effectively than continued Dmab, although CTX suppression remains incomplete [17]. Thus, the work of Bolamperti and colleagues, along with these findings, strengthens our understanding of a metronomic BP regimen [21].

In detail, when denosumab is absolutely to stop, our approach involves administering an oral amino-BP (e.g., ALN) at low doses and/or with extended intervals ('metronomic' vs. standard dose), aiming to avoid excessive resorption and maintain normal osteoclast function. The choice between dose or interval management may depend on the patient's preference, clinician judgment (e.g., based on fracture risk), and, ideally, on future mechanistic and clinical ad hoc studies. Our idea is to help prevent an antiresorptive overshoot that could reduce the anabolic capacity of osteoclasts. Thus, during this phase, Zol cannot be used due to its long half-life and prolonged effects, which prevent accurate modulation.

The second agent we chose to combine with the BP is Abalo, a selective analog of parathyroid hormone-related peptide (PTHrP). Our choice is that, when compared to TPTD, Abalo provides a more favorable balance between bone formation and resorption, with less stimulation of osteoclastogenesis, primarily attributed to its high selectivity for the "RG" conformation of the parathyroid hormone 1 receptor (PTH1R). This leads to more transient, mainly anabolic signaling while reducing osteoclastic activation [16]. Ideally, thanks to the metronomic BP, Abalo might utilize preserved coupling signals to enhance bone formation, while BP keeps resorption under control.

The complementary tool considered for this approach, despite several limitations, is CTX monitoring. Although thresholds such as 0.280 ng/mL or the suggested 0.212 ng/mL [7,9] have been proposed, their clinical use remains inconsistent. Fixed cutoffs may not fully account for factors like age, sex, ethnicity, or the relatively high reference change value (RCV, approximately 30%) of this analyte, as well as conditions like chronic kidney disease (CKD) or sample collection timing, especially if not after a morning fast. Moreover, data linking these thresholds to fracture outcomes are limited or absent. Therefore, without new evidence and markers, we can consider 0.280 ng/mL as a tentative standard CTX alert level – not as the therapeutic threshold, which is always a complex decision made by clinicians rather than based solely on analyte levels – while emphasizing that this marker should always be interpreted considering individual characteristics, baseline values, and local laboratory medians for age and sex, with greater focus on longitudinal trends rather than single readings [25] (see Figure 1). When baseline or median values are clearly unsuitable targets (for example, abnormally high) or if local data are unavailable, the cutoff of 0.280 ng/mL may be regarded as the most reliable choice. Additionally, it's not possible to determine the optimal timing for monitoring and treatment in advance because each patient is unique and every case is unpredictable. Therefore, clinicians should also decide when to monitor CTX, which varies on a case-by-case basis and depends on the time since Dmab

discontinuation (e.g., every 6 months for low-risk patients, every 2-3 months for high-risk patients, or more frequently in cases of incident fractures), paying attention to any elevation of CTX that could be related to the fracture itself.

Figure 1. A pragmatic framework for CTX interpretation after denosumab discontinuation.

Legend fig. 1. Pragmatic framework for interpreting serum CTX (C-terminal telopeptide) trend after denosumab discontinuation. The target zone (green) corresponds to the patient's baseline or local median, reflecting (theoretically) 'physiological' remodeling. The caution zone (yellow) represents CTX values above baseline but below the universal alert threshold. The alert zone (red) is defined as CTX over 0.280 ng/mL, a level consistently associated with rebound bone loss and increased risk of vertebral fractures. This conceptual model supports personalized, trend-based monitoring and guides the modulation of metronomic bisphosphonate-abaloparatide therapy. When evaluating every CTX value, consider pitfalls (sample, incident fracture, chronic kidney disease, intrinsic high reference change value, etc.). For these reasons, always prefer trends over single values.

Thus, we hypothesize that metronomic BP combined in a first phase with Abalo therapy, guided by personalized CTX monitoring, may serve as an effective and mechanistically coherent strategy (see Figure 2). The BP-Abalo combination phase should last no more than 12 months, in line with both the approved treatment period and Abalo's peak anabolic activity. After this time, Abalo should be discontinued, based on the current knowledge and regulatory approval.

Figure 2. Conceptual CTX trajectories after denosumab discontinuation.

Legend fig. 2. Conceptual model of serum CTX (C-terminal telopeptide) dynamics after denosumab discontinuation under different strategies. Bisphosphonate-only consolidation (blue) partially suppresses resorption but often fails to maintain CTX below the alert threshold. Anabolic-only therapy (red) paradoxically amplifies rebound resorption, leading to pronounced CTX oscillations. The proposed metronomic bisphosphonate–abaloparatide combination (green) aims to restrain CTX within a controlled range, thereby preserving physiologic remodeling signals and offering a biologically coherent approach to prevent rebound-associated fractures.

Subsequently, a maintenance phase with an amino-BP alone (or other agents) may be pursued, likely in most cases, depending on the patient’s choice, clinical profile, comorbidities, and life expectancy, to avoid overtreatment in older adults and long-term high-dose treatment in the youngest (due to the lack of long-term safety data for repeated Zol infusions in non-oncological settings or other novel regimens, like ours). Additionally, consider baseline and evolving fracture risk, Dmab therapy duration, the occurrence of new fragility fractures, and longitudinal trends in CTX, BMD (evaluated every 18-24 months), and the bone quality index (e.g., TBS, assessed during DXA scans). These factors are crucial for selecting the agent and determining the duration of BP-only therapy (e.g., 12 months or longer), which also helps decide whether to continue with the same drug or switch to another BP (e.g., Zol) or an alternative class, whether oral or injectable. Thus, personalization is essential. For example, an extreme case of a patients who sustain new fractures may require changes, prolongation, or intensification of therapy, including sequential or cyclic regimens beyond our standard approach (even the reinitiation of Dmab). Conversely, lower-risk individuals may be candidates for gradual tapering supported by structured biochemical and densitometric monitoring (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Simplified version of the proposed sequential therapy.

Legend fig. 3. This schematic illustrates the personalized, phase-based approach to optimize bone remodeling. Treatment begins with metronomic oral bisphosphonate (BP) combined with abaloparatide (Abalo) for a maximum of 12 months, leveraging Abalo’s selective anabolic action and the preservation of osteoclast function through low-dose BP. This is followed by a maintenance phase, typically lasting ≥ 12 months, using oral BP, intravenous (IV) BP, or other agents, selected based on the patient’s clinical profile and on the monitoring. Throughout and beyond treatment, clinical decisions are guided by trends in CTX (C-terminal telopeptide), BMD (bone mineral density), and TBS (trabecular bone score), as well as fracture risk and new fracture occurrence. While a CTX level less than 0.280 ng/mL may be used as an alert threshold, all values, thresholds, and monitoring intervals should be individually tailored, considering baseline values, intraindividual variability, and contextual clinical factors.

Conclusions

Discontinuing Dmab exposes patients to a severe rebound in bone turnover, rapid loss of BMD, and a high risk of multiple VFs. Current consolidation strategies only offer partial and inconsistent protection, and once rebound fractures happen, treatment options are limited, and the prognosis is poor.

Based on biological insights, we propose a theoretical strategy of metronomic BP therapy combined with Abalo. It is a more effective and biologically consistent approach because it limits, but does not entirely stop, osteoclast activity; thus, our method may prevent rebound-related fractures while maintaining the anabolic potential of bone remodeling.

Once again, our approach remains a working experimental hypothesis that requires rigorous clinical validation. However, it offers a new conceptual framework for safely discontinuing Dmab, proposing a paradigm shift from static suppression to dynamic, clinical-, imaging-, and biomarker-guided modulation of bone remodeling.

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Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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